

Plastic pollution in food packaging systems: impact on human health, socioeconomic considerations and regulatory framework

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ABSTRACT

Global plastic production surpasses 400 million metric tons annually. With only 9 % being recycled, 50 % directly landfilled, and an additional 20 % mismanaged, plastic waste represents a major challenge facing our planet today. The repercussions of plastic pollution are extensive, affecting the future of sustainability globally, by not only the environment and human health but also socioeconomic and sociocultural factors. This review examines the effects of macro and microplastics on various human organs and systems, including the liver, brain, stem cells, respiratory, reproductive, immune, and neurological systems. It also investigates the different routes of microplastic uptake, such as digestion, inhalation, and dermal contact. These routes highlight how microplastics with size ranges less than 3 μm can infiltrate the body, causing oxidative stress, inflammation, and cellular dysfunction as well as differentiation shift of stem cells, which may lead to chronic health conditions. Moreover, this study highlights the urgent need for implementing sustainable practices, policies, and regulations to address the health risks, economic losses, diminished quality of life, disruption of traditional practices, and impacts on cultural heritage and community well-being. By emphasizing the interconnectedness of environmental, health, and societal factors, this review highlights the urgency of adopting a comprehensive approach to mitigate the impacts of plastic pollution. Addressing this global challenge is crucial not only to safeguard public health but also to ensure the sustainability of our planet's future.

1. Introduction

Various research efforts are tackling many challenges that complicate the achievement of sustainability, with plastic pollution standing out as a major issue affecting the environmental, economic, and social pillars of sustainability. In 2022, global plastic production surged to an unprecedented 400 million metric tons, marking a 1.6 percent increase from the previous year. This exponential growth rise is part of a long-standing trend in plastic manufacturing that began in the 1950s (Statista et Statista, 2024). If this trend persists, plastic manufacturing is projected to hit 26 billion metric tons by 2050 (Geyer et al., 2017; Guglielmi, 2017). Among the polymers driving this surge are

high-density polyethylene (HDPE), low-density polyethylene (LDPE), polyethylene terephthalate (PET), polystyrene (PS) and polyvinyl chloride (PVC) which together account for approximately 90 % of the global plastic production (Andrady and Neal, 2009). For instance, in wastewater treatment plants, PS and PET particles are among the most common microplastics (MPs), reflecting their widespread use in food packaging and other applications. Moreover, PET is frequently detected in the sludge of treatment plants, primarily due to its extensive application as a food packaging material. These findings underscore the pervasive nature of these plastics and their ability to enter various environmental compartments (Kamani et al., 2024a; 2024b). Despite their durability, large marine plastics such as packaging, fishing nets,

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and car tires break down over time through processes like photodegradation, wave erosion, contact with marine organisms, abrasion by sand, and exposure to water (Eriksen et al., 2014). Plastic debris in the environment can be classified into four categories based on their sizes: microplastics (MPs) (less than 0.5 cm), mesoplastics (0.5 to 5 cm), macroplastics (5 to 50 cm), and megaplastics (greater than 50 cm) (Lebreton et al., 2018 Mar; Hamd et al., 2022). Large plastic debris, known as macroplastics, have been present in the marine environment since the onset of plastic production (Derriak, 2002). Most of the plastic that persists in the environment will eventually decompose into smaller particles. This breakdown is driven by various factors, including mechanical degradation, biological processes, and photooxidation (Amato-Lourenço et al., 2020). Furthermore, MPs are increasingly being recognized as pollutants of concern because they enter the environment not only through plastic debris breakdown but also via wastewater treatment plants. Therefore, the effects of MPs on the environment are widespread, impacting both aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems. MPs disrupt food webs, accumulate in marine sediments, and contaminate soils, affecting microbial communities, plant growth, overall environmental health and act as carriers for toxic pollutants (Kamani et al., 2024; Woodall et al., 2014; Eerkes-Medrano et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2020; 2020; Enyoh et al., 2019; Corradini et al., 2019). Moreover, Small plastic particles have also been detected at low level of 30 to 50 particles in the organs and tissues of various aquatic organisms, such as fish (Su et al., 2019), mussels (Browne et al., 2008) crustaceans (Cui et al., 2017) and zooplankton (Sharma et S Chatterjee, 2017). Thus, MPs can easily facilitate the transfer of pollutants along the food chain ultimately impacting human health (Uheida et al., 2021; Teuten et al., 2009). This review explores the impact of both macroplastic and MPs debris on human health, aiming to highlight how these pollutants enter the human body and their health implications. It also focuses on the impact of plastic pollution on the socioeconomic and sociocultural considerations along with policies, regulations and effective mitigation strategies that are essential for promoting sustainability in addressing these concerns.

2. Health implications of plastics used in food packaging

The overall demand for plastic in Europe in 2018 amounted to 51.2 million metric tons. Of this total, 20.5 million metric tons were allocated for general packaging, while 8.2 million metric tons were dedicated to the food sector (Statista 2021). Since their inception in food packaging, these materials swiftly supplanted traditional options like glass, wood and metal driven by their numerous perceived advantages. In today's interconnected food network, food contact articles and food contact materials such as tableware, processing equipment and packaging are ubiquitous, particularly those manufactured from plastic (Chakori et al., 2021; Poças et al., 2009). However, plastics are not inert, and smaller molecules can migrate from plastic packaging into food (Muncke et al., 2020; Hahladakis et al., 2018). This is particularly concerning food stored in plastic sachets or containers where direct contact with the inner surface of the packaging increases the risk of substances transfer or reactions with the food. This contact can result in the potential transfer of harmful substances from plastic into the food, thereby exposing consumers to these contaminants upon consumption. The movement of various chemicals from plastic food packaging materials into food is commonly referred to as migration. This process typically involves four stages: (I) diffusion of chemical substances through the polymer; (II) release of molecules from the surface of the polymer; (III) binding of compounds at the interface between plastic and food; and (IV) uptake of substances by the food itself (Hahladakis et al., 2018; Cruz et al., 2019). Consequently, plastic packaging is a significant source of human exposure to manufactured chemicals, raising concerns about the sustainability of its use, especially given the dangerous chemicals involved in plastic production (Geueke et al., 2018). Indeed, plastic packaging consists not only of polymer chains but also includes various additives. These additives, typically added in small quantities during

manufacturing, improve the mechanical properties, flexibility, durability, stability, and color of the packaging, or facilitate its production and handling. However, a major concern is that packaging, intended to protect food, can become a source of chemical contamination. Additionally, the weathering and degradation of plastic materials can cause these compounds to leach into seawater, where they may be ingested by organisms (Cole et al., 2011). Numerous chemical additives utilized in plastic manufacturing pose significant risks to human health (Lithner et al., 2011). Among these, Phthalates are widely recognized as some of the most harmful chemical additives in plastics due to their significant health risks. Studies have highlighted their widespread application in plastic manufacturing (Groh et al., 2019), their high potential for release during recycling activities (Geueke et al., 2018), and their substantial risks to human health (Hahladakis et al., 2018). Phthalates are capable of penetrating human tissues, leading to adverse health effects. Known as endocrine disruptors, phthalates are capable of imitating or disrupting hormones in the body contributing to various health issues such as hormonal imbalances, asthma, obesity, early puberty, and endometriosis (Durmaz et al., 2018). They impact the hypothalamic-pituitary-gonadal axis, disrupting the production of sex hormones, which can lead to reproductive issues such as cryptorchidism and hypospadias (Csaba, 2018; Hliseníková et al., 2020). Phthalates can also influence erythrocytes by inducing hemolysis, oxidative stress, and changes in hemoglobin structure, which may lead to anemia and immune system dysfunction (Sicińska et al., 2020; Zhou et al., 2020; Labow et al., 1987). In the reproductive systems of both men and women, phthalates have been shown to reduce sperm motility and concentration in men, causing malformations like testicular dysgenesis, while in women, they can lead to early puberty, endometriosis, and polycystic ovary syndrome (Hliseníková et al., 2020), (Gray et al., 2006; Chou et al., 2009; Reddy et al., 2006; Pednekar et al., 2018; Ventrice et al., 2013). Exposure to phthalates can have long-lasting effects on reproductive health, and their widespread presence in various consumer products makes them a constant risk. In the present day, for the sake of convenience in transportation, storage, and extended shelf life, people frequently use plastic containers, water bottles, cups, cans, and wraps. Additionally, glass bottles and aluminum cans with inner linings made of plastic materials have become popular choices for food storage (Fadare et al., 2020). However, these plastic packaging products, which can further complicate sustainability challenges, are leaching MPs into our foods, which are then ingested by people (Bouwmeester et al., 2015).

3. Microplastics routes of uptake

In 2004, the term "microplastics" (Thompson et al., 2004) was coined, referring to small plastic fragments, both granular and fibrous, typically around 20 µm in size. The increasing accumulation of MPs in the environment has raised significant concerns about human exposure through food.

MPs can be classified into primary and secondary types based on their sources. Primary MPs are intentionally produced to be small in size, typically for use in cosmetic products like microbeads or in industries (Hartmann et al., 2019; Browne et al., 2011) while secondary MPs are particles that have been fragmented through processes such as mechanical weathering or photodegradation. MPs are present throughout all environmental domains, encompassing the atmosphere, aquatic and terrestrial environments, and are found in food sources, marine organisms, drinking water, fruit and vegetables (Conti et al., 2020; Van Cauwenberghe et al., 2014). They have also been identified in tea bags, sea salt, sugar, honey, beer (Barboza et al., 2020) and numerous other food items. Moreover, they have been detected in the gastrointestinal tracts of marine animals, highlighting the environmental impact of plastic pollution on marine ecosystems. Indeed, sea food and fish represent a crucial way for humans to get exposed. These MP particles threaten sustainability by infiltrating the human body

through the food chain in affecting human health and by contaminating environments, which disrupts the broader ecological balance.

Certainly, MPs can penetrate the human body via three main pathways: inhalation, ingestion and possibly through epidermal contact, prompting concerns about potential detrimental health consequences. The presence of MPs in various food products has raised concerns about human ingestion of these particles, which can also occur through inhalation, as they are found in both indoor and outdoor air environments (Gasperi et al., 2018). Therefore, on average, human are exposed to approximately 26 to 130 airborne MP particles per day through inhalation (Prata, 2018). In addition, MPs come into contact with humans through dermal contact as they are present in cosmetic products like toothpaste, facial cleansers, and scrubs where they serve as exfoliants for the teeth and skin (Strand, 2014; Hernandez et al., 2017).

3.1. Microplastics uptake by digestion (food web chain)

Currently, oral ingestion is the main pathway of exposure, with recent research revealing significant amounts of MP particles in food, drinking water, and from the regular use of materials that come into contact with food. In food products, PET, PE, PS, and PP represent the majority of detected MPs, accounting for over 50 % of the total MPs found (Hurt et al., 2020; Lusher et al., 2013; Tanaka et al., 2016; Cheung et al., 2018; Kim et al., 2018; Nan et al., 2020; Waddell et al., 2020). Indeed, an assessment of MPs intake from average food consumption indicated an annual average ingestion of approximately 39,000 to 52,000 particles (Cox et al., 2019). These particles can enter the gastrointestinal system through contaminated food. MPs have been detected in food such as water (Oßmann et al., 2018), fruits and vegetables (Conti et al., 2020), fish and bivalves (Barboza et al., 2020), sugar (Liebezeit et al., 2013) and table salt (Karami et al., 2017). After ingestion, particles may be absorbed in the intestine through specialized M-cells (Ensign et al., 2012). Given the contamination of our food and environment with MPs, it is very likely that humans are exposed to them through ingestion and other sources.

3.2. Microplastics uptake by inhalation (flying particles)

Several studies have demonstrated that MPs are found in the atmosphere and can be effortlessly inhaled (Huang et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2019). Indeed, MPs are dispersed into the air from multiple origins, such as synthetic fabrics, the wear and tear of materials and the resuspension of MPs from surfaces. Furthermore, according to Liu et al. (Liu et al., 2019) people in Shanghai breathe around 21 MP particles per day when outdoors. During outdoor activities, it is estimated that children may be exposed to nearly 3223 MP particles per year, whereas adults may face an exposure of around 1063 MP particles annually (Abbasi et al., 2019). The potential for inhaling MPs is influenced by their size, with smaller particles being more likely to enter and affect the respiratory system. Particles smaller than 10µm are particularly concerning because they can more easily penetrate epithelial barriers and interact with cells and tissues, potentially leading to adverse health effects. Moreover, the shape of MPs is also crucial, with evidence suggesting that fibrous MPs are especially capable of reaching deeper regions of the lungs, increasing the risk of respiratory issues (Amato-Lourenço et al., 2020; Prata, 2018), (Prata et al., 2020). Although the majority of fibers can be removed from the respiratory system, those that remain have the potential to induce inflammatory responses and respiratory lesions, particularly among individuals with compromised clearance mechanisms (Gasperi et al., 2018; Prata, 2018). The development of airway and interstitial lung diseases in synthetic textile workers has been linked to occupational exposure to airborne MPs (Pimentel et al., 1975).

3.3. Microplastics uptake by dermal contact

Contact with MPs through the skin is regarded as a less significant pathway of exposure. Despite the fact that the stratum corneum, the outermost layer of the skin, acts as a defensive barrier against harmful substances when healthy (Schneider et al., 2009), it is hypothesized that nanoplastics (NPs) may still be able to penetrate this dermal barrier (Revel et al., 2018). The damaging effects of skin contact with MPs have not been assessed, highlighting the need for further research. This pathway of MPs intake has not been thoroughly investigated or documented, likely due to concerns about ethical constraints, sample biosecurity and methodological limitations.

As discussed above, MPs may access the human body via several exposure pathways. These uptake mechanisms are summarized in Fig. 1.

4. Microplastics and their health repercussions

Microplastics have infiltrated nearly every facet of our environment, leading to growing concerns about their potential effects on human health. Once ingested, inhaled, or absorbed, these microscopic particles interact with various physiological systems, often with harmful consequences. This section delves into the diverse health repercussions of microplastics, exploring their effects on critical systems such as the respiratory, hepatic, reproductive, immune, and neurological systems. Furthermore, we examine their impact on cellular processes, including stem cell function, shedding light on the broader implications for overall health and well-being.

4.1. Breathing in the invisible: respiratory system impacts

A recent study has demonstrated that acute exposure to PE was tested on human bronchial epithelial cells (BEAS-2B) and alveolar epithelial cells (A549) at concentrations of 25 µg/mL and 100 µg/mL for 24 h. PE induced epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT) and increased migration in both cell lines. These findings suggest a potential role for PE in carcinogenesis. Additionally, another study found that exposure to PET microplastics led to cytotoxic effects in lung epithelial cells, including reduced cell viability and increased oxidative stress, highlighting the broader impact of various microplastics on respiratory health. These findings underscore the potential health risks associated with inhalation of microplastics and their role in respiratory diseases (Traversa et al., 2024; Rahman et al., 2024; Vasse and Melgert, 2024).

After gaining access to the human body via the respiratory and digestive systems, MPs breach the epithelial barrier and disperse throughout multiple organs (Prata et al., 2020). Multiple studies have confirmed the presence of MPs in lung tissues (Amato-Lourenço et al., 2020), (Jenner et al., 2022). Additionally, research has shown that PP and PE are the most prevalent particles found in lung tissue, owing to their widespread use in manufacturing (Statista 2020). In fact, epidemiological research has shown that workers in the plastic and textile industries who are exposed to relatively large quantity of MPs, suffer from lung damage, such as allergies, inflammation and fibrosis (Wright and Kelly, 2017). These results prove that the respiratory system is a route of exposure and that the lungs act as a site for the accumulation of MPs in humans. This buildup of MPs can have harmful effects. Indeed, inhalation of MPs may lead to lung dysfunction. The latter has been confirmed in studies on human lung epithelial BEAS-2B cells, which have shown that PS MPs can induce cytotoxic and inflammatory responses by generating reactive oxygen species (ROS). Additionally, a decrease in transepithelial electrical resistance has been observed, due to the depletion of zonula occludens proteins (Dong et al., 2020). Moreover, PE, PP, PS, and PVC MPs were assessed for their ability to induce senescence and oxidative stress in human lung cells in vitro. At concentrations of 0.5 and 5 µg/mL, MPs significantly increased the proportion of SA-β-gal-positive cells, with PE and PVC having the strongest effects, leading to approximately 70 % senescent cells after 48

Fig. 1. Mechanism of MPs uptake by digestion, inhalation and dermal contact [80–81].

h of treatment. These treatments also elevated the expression of senescence markers p16 and p21, enhanced the secretion of Senescence-Associated Secretory Phenotype (SASP) factors (TNF- α , IL-6, and IL-1 β), and triggered a notable increase in ROS, highlighting the role of oxidative stress in the senescence process. Similar trends were observed in BEAS-2B bronchial epithelial cells, confirming that MPs promote ROS production and cellular senescence in lung-related cells in a dose- and time-dependent manner (Jin et al., 2024). Yong et al. had also demonstrated that MPs inhalation leads to a range of biological impacts comprising cellular damage, oxidative stress, senescence, inflammation, cytokine secretion and immune responses (Yong et al., 2020; Luo et al., 2023). This causes lung inflammation, impairs the pulmonary epithelial barrier, and subsequently contributes to the development and progression of various lung diseases including pulmonary fibrosis, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and asthma (Dong et al., 2020; Luo et al., 2023; Lu et al., 2021; Li et al., 2022; 2022). In addition, Zhang et al. investigated the lung toxicity and pulmonary fibrosis induced by PS-MPs in mice. In their study, 80 six-week-old female C57BL/6 mice were exposed to PS MPs (5 μ m) via daily intranasal administration for four weeks. The results showed that PS-MPs exposure led to oxidative stress, ferroptosis, and the activation of the cGAS/STING pathway, which contributed to the development of pulmonary fibrosis (Zhang et al., 2024).

4.2. Hepatotoxicity

The liver plays a vital role as one of the primary organs responsible for detoxification in the body. The human hepatocellular carcinoma (HepG2) cell line has been utilized in numerous studies as an in vitro model of the human liver. Researchers have chosen HepG2 cells for their ability to mimic certain aspects of human liver physiology and function, making them valuable tools for investigating various aspects of liver biology. Recent research has highlighted that the presence of MPs leads to significant cytotoxic effects on HepG2 cells, notably inducing severe damage to cell membranes (Wang et al., 2022; Stock et al., 2020). The liver is particularly vulnerable to damage from MPs due to its unique structure, specifically the hepatic portal vein that links directly to gastrointestinal blood vessels. Recent investigations have revealed that MPs can cause liver inflammation, lysosomal damage, oxidative stress, mitochondrial impairment, and increased lipid accumulation (Liang et al., 2022; Chi et al., 2022; Yin et al., 2023). It has also been demonstrated that MPs cause liver damage, disrupt metabolic enzymes and lipid metabolism in liver organoids (LOs) derived from human pluripotent stem cells. Moreover, MPs trigger the generation of reactive oxygen species, leading to oxidative stress, development of liver fibrosis and

an inflammatory response, which underscores their lipotoxic effects (Cheng et al., 2022; Shen et al., 2022). They equally enhance glutamine and glutamate synthesis in the liver while suppressing the Nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2 (Nrf2) signalling pathway, thereby decreasing antioxidant capacity (Yin et al., 2022). Furthermore, PS with a diameter of 1 μ m have been identified as a cause of hepatotoxicity in human liver organoids (HBOs) after 48 h of exposure. This includes damage to hepatocytes, disruption of lipid metabolism, and alterations in bile acid regulation. Accumulation of PS in bile ducts was observed, facilitated by ursodeoxycholic acid (UDCA), which promotes bile flow through the activation of bile transporters such as BSEP and MRP-2. However, when these transporters were inhibited by troglitazone, the clearance of PS was reduced, leading to increased hepatotoxicity. These results emphasize the protective role of bile transporters against microplastic-induced liver damage and provide valuable insights into potential therapeutic strategies to mitigate such effects (Li et al., 2024). Additionally, PS causes slight acute toxicity in normal human liver cells (THLE-2) at concentrations below 20 μ g/mL but induce chronic toxicity at environmentally relevant doses (0.2 μ g/mL) over 90 days. Metabolomic analysis revealed significant alterations in the cells' metabolic profiles, particularly with nanosized MPs (0.1 μ m) (Chen et al., 2024).

4.3. Stealthy disruptors: impacts on the reproductive system

MPs can potentially affect the reproductive development of humans, as they can enter the bloodstream from the maternal respiratory system and access the placenta. The placenta is essential for the transfer of nutrients and waste products between maternal and foetal bloodstreams, highlighting the potential risk MPs pose to foetal development (Schlesinger et al., 1988; Ragusa et al., 2021; Turco and Moffett, 2019). Indeed, exposure to MPs has been shown to induce inflammation, cell cycle arrest, DNA damage, and apoptosis in placental cells (Shen et al., 2022). Similarly, in human ovarian cells, PS nanoparticles decreased mitochondrial membrane potential and cell viability, increased oxidative stress and apoptosis, and ultimately caused cell cycle arrest (Huang et al., 2023). A recent study demonstrated that PS could penetrate ovarian granulosa cells, inhibiting cell proliferation, inducing oxidative stress, and promoting apoptosis (Zeng et al., 2023). Additionally, maternal exposure to MPs profoundly affects progeny across multiple domains, leading to neurological deficits, weight loss, circulatory abnormalities, developmental malformations, metabolic disorders, reproductive failure and immune disturbances (Huang et al., 2023; Zeng et al., 2023; Hu et al., 2021; Bringer et al., 2020). Hu et al. reported that PS can enter both the cytoplasm and nucleus of trophoblastic cells, leading to decreased cell viability and increased ROS levels. PS also

causes cell cycle arrest, reduces trophoblast migration, induces the production of proinflammatory cytokines, and affects gene expression patterns in the trophoblast cell line (Hu et al., 2022). MPs have also been found in the testis and human semen (Zhao et al., 2023; Montano et al., 2023). Thus, PS MPs have substantial toxic effects on the reproductive system, reducing both sperm quality and testosterone levels. Additionally, PS induces inflammation in the testes and disrupts the blood-testis barrier (Jin et al., 2021). They lead to sperm acrosome defects and a reduction in serum testosterone levels, which is linked to increased ROS production, resulting in oxidative stress and cell apoptosis (Zhou et al., 2022; Sun et al., 2023). Recent research has identified the presence of MPs in human testes, with total concentrations averaging 328.44 µg/g. PE was the most prevalent polymer type, and correlations between polymers such as PVC and PET with testis weight were observed, highlighting the widespread contamination of the male reproductive system. Furthermore, an analysis of MPs in human semen and urine found that exposure to various plastic types was associated with a decrease in sperm count and motility, indicating a potential reproductive health risk due to microplastic pollution (Hu et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2024). According to the study conducted by Qin et al. MPs ranging from 2 to 200 µm in size were identified in human endometrial tissues. These MPs were primarily composed of polyamide (PA), polyurethane (PU), PET, PP, PS, and PE. The study highlighted two main pathways for MPs to reach the uterus: smaller particles (0.1–10 µm) enter via the bloodstream following absorption through the digestive system, while larger particles (>50 µm) infiltrate through the vaginal canal and uterine lacunae. The presence of MPs in the human endometrium was associated with adverse effects, including disrupted cellular development and increased rates of apoptosis, as demonstrated in human endometrial organoid models. These findings raise concerns about the impact of MP contamination on human reproductive health and fertility (Qin et al., 2024).

4.4. Immune system under assault

Human exposure to MPs can stimulate the body's immune response. Indeed, the immune system consists of various cells and components that shield us from harmful foreign entities, including pathogens and MPs. Moreover, Yang et al. (Yang et al., 2023) demonstrated that MPs/NPs can impact the immune system in several ways, including the activation of the inflammasome. Also, MPs can enter the systemic circulation and influence the immune response via the gut-lung axis (Enaud et al., 2020). Exposure to MPs has been shown to activate immune cells, leading to an increased production of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF-α and IL-6. In a related study by Han et al. (Han et al., 2020) the effects of specific plastic polymers, PVC and acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS), were investigated. The study revealed that a 4 to 5-day exposure to PVC and ABS triggered immune responses in human immune cells. Notably, both PVC and ABS were found to suppress histamine release, while simultaneously enhancing the secretion of pro-inflammatory cytokines, including IL-6 and TNF-α. These findings highlight the potential immunomodulatory effects of various plastic materials, suggesting that MPs, like PVC and ABS, could contribute to chronic inflammation and immune system disruption. Similarly, a study by Adler et al. revealed that PS, ranging from 0.5 µm to 3 µm, significantly affect human macrophages. PS were shown to influence metabolic activity in a size- and concentration-dependent manner, with smaller particles (0.5 µm) causing more pronounced effects. Higher concentrations of PS increased cytotoxicity, with significant necrosis observed at 37.5 µg/mL after 24 and 48 h of exposure. While general reactive oxygen species levels were not significantly altered, nitric oxide (NO) production a type of reactive nitrogen species increased in a concentration-dependent manner. These findings emphasize the potential immunotoxic effects of MPs on human immune cells, highlighting the risks posed by microplastic pollution on human health (Adler et al., 2024).

4.5. Microplastics and neurological health: insights into brain function

MPs can penetrate the blood-brain barrier in vivo (Yang et al., 2004) and be internalized by neuronal cells in vitro (Zauner et al., 2001; Kulkarni and Feng, 2013). These findings suggest that MPs exposure can result in their distribution throughout the body and accumulation in the brain. Notably, research indicates that a 24-hour exposure of human glioblastoma multiforme cell line (T98 G) to PS (10 µm, 0.05–10 mg/L) result in an increase in reactive oxygen species (Schirinzi et al., 2017). Additionally, studies have demonstrated that a 24-hour exposure to PS, with sizes ranging from 45 to 70 nm, in neuronal cells leads to significant neuroinflammation, disrupts mitochondrial activity, and causes an increase in lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) leakage, confirming the detrimental effects of PS on cellular function and overall cell health (Murali et al., 2015). Emerging evidence suggests a correlation between oxidative stress and inflammation in the central nervous system and various neurodegenerative disorders such as Huntington disease, Parkinson, Alzheimer and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (Tönnies et al., Trushina, 2017; Radi et al., 2014). This highlights the potential for exposure to micro- and nanoplastics to potentially trigger or exacerbate these neurodegenerative diseases. Furthermore, a recent study has demonstrated that the oral intake of NPs adversely affects brain behaviors and immune function by stimulating the intestinal IL-1 signaling pathway, pointing to a potential involvement of the gut-brain axis in brain dysfunction induced by NPs (Lee et al., 2023; Yang et al., 2023). Additionally, the build-up of NPs in the prefrontal cortex has been associated with decreased neuronal branching (Suman et al., 2024), and they may increase the risk of Parkinson's disease by reducing ATP-related genes and proteins (Liang et al., 2022). Paing et al. (Paing et al., 2024) showed that exposure to MPs might be an environmental factor that contributes to cognitive impairments related to neurodegenerative diseases, primarily by initiating or exacerbating microglial activation and neuroinflammation. After 24 h of exposure to a concentration of 200 µg/mL of PS MPs, significant accumulation in microglial cells triggered activation and inflammatory responses. This resulted in suppressed hippocampal neuronal activity, indicating a potential link between PS exposure, neuroinflammation, and cognitive deficits. Furthermore, prolonged exposure to PS led to a significant increase in pro-inflammatory cytokines and a reduction in synaptic plasticity, further supporting the hypothesis that MPs may play a role in the pathogenesis of neurodegenerative diseases by affecting brain function and structure. Additionally, exposure to MPs led to their accumulation in the brain, activation of microglia, and neuron damage, also in human cerebral microvascular endothelial cells, MPs caused oxidative stress, inflammatory responses, necroptosis, disrupted tight junctions, and demonstrated the ability to penetrate cell layers (Shan et al., 2022). When neurons are exposed to MPs, it can lead to elevated ROS production, which leads to cellular damage and heightened neuroinflammation in the brain (Prüst et al., 2020). The detrimental effects of MP particles are evident through their capacity to induce significant stress at both intercellular and intracellular levels, particularly affecting the differentiation of cortical layers in embryonic brain-like tissues. Exposure to PS MPs, at different concentrations (100, 50, and 5 µg/mL) and sizes (1 µm and 10 µm) during both short-term (day 4–10) and long-term (day 4–30) periods, disrupts normal cellular functions, leading to diminished cell viability over extended periods. This disruption is characterized by changes in the expression of neural progenitor and mature neuronal markers, highlighting potential risks of neurotoxicity and degeneration to human health (Hua et al., 2022). These findings emphasize the critical need to evaluate and mitigate the environmental presence of MPs to safeguard neurological development and overall well-being.

4.6. Stem cells in peril: implications for cellular health

Stem cells are distributed across various organs and tissues, including the blood, skin, muscle, brain and bone marrow (Anderson

et al., 2001), highlighting their widespread presence in the body. This ubiquitous distribution underscores the significant potential for environmental MP particles to influence stem cell activity. Indeed, MPs were detected in the bone marrow, indicating their ability to cross barriers and disrupt hematopoietic homeostasis (Jing et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2023; Jani et al., 1990). Recent studies have found that MPs can disrupt the balance of gut microbiota, alter metabolism, and promote inflammation, leading to hematopoietic damage (Jing et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2023). Moreover, Leslie et al. (Leslie et al., 2022) demonstrated the presence of plastic particles in the human bloodstream, providing robust evidence of plastic contamination in the human body. Additionally, research involving humans has demonstrated the transfer of MPs from the intestine to the lymphatic system (Kannan et K. Vimalkumar 2021). Furthermore, Jiang et al. (Jiang et al., 2024) identified MPs in the gastrointestinal tract and peripheral blood, where they impaired the self-renewal of hematopoietic stem cells by altering the gut microbiota and its metabolic products. It is necessary to mention that MP particles play a crucial role in influencing stem cell behavior, oxidative stress responses, and cytotoxic effects (Im et al., 2022). Moreover exposure to MPs has been shown to alter the fate of mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) in vitro, triggering senescence and leading to the loss of multiple stem cell characteristics (Najahi et al., 2022). Indeed, exposure to PET sizes $<1 \mu\text{m}$ and $<2.6 \mu\text{m}$ has been linked to decreased proliferation in both adipocyte mesenchymal stem cells and bone marrow mesenchymal stem cells. Furthermore, MPs have been found to generate accumulation of reactive oxygen species in MSCs, contributing to unrepaired DNA damage (Najahi et al., 2022). Stojkovic et al. (Stojkovic et al., 2023) demonstrated that human induced pluripotent stem cells and fibroblast treated for 24 h with 40 nm PS microplastics at a concentration of $8.52 \times$

10^{10} particles/ml showed significant changes. Specifically, they observed alterations in the Estrogen Related Receptor Beta (ESRRB) and Hepatocyte nuclear factor 1-alpha (HNF1A) pathways, which are crucial for maintaining stem cell pluripotency. These changes also affected pathways related to carbohydrate metabolism, inflammatory disorders and gluconeogenesis. The exposure of neural stem cells (NSCs) to MPs at concentrations of 5 and $10 \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ showed the following results: The positively charged PS with sizes of $0.1 \mu\text{m}$, $1 \mu\text{m}$, and $2 \mu\text{m}$ decreased cell viability and proliferation. The amine-modified MPs also reduced neurogenesis and oligodendrogenesis and caused damage to fully differentiated neurons and oligodendrocytes (Park et al., 2024). Additionally, Zhou et al. (Zhou et al., 2024) demonstrated that exposure of iPSC-derived kidney organoids to PS ($1 \mu\text{m}$) significantly impacts early human kidney development. The organoids were treated with PS during the nephron progenitor cell (NPC) stage, a critical phase in kidney formation. The study found that PS-MPs adhered to the cell surfaces and accumulated in structures resembling glomeruli, leading to a reduction in organoid size and irregular nephron development. Both short- and long-term exposure to PS-MPs resulted in increased production of reactive oxygen species, triggering NPC apoptosis and lowering cell viability. Similarly, a recent study investigating human neural stem cells (hNS1) exposed to 30 nm PS at concentrations of 0.5, 2.5, and $10 \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ for 4 days also revealed significant biological effects. This exposure induced oxidative stress, DNA damage, apoptosis, and inflammatory responses, further highlighting the detrimental impact of MP particles on stem cell function. Together, these findings emphasize the broader implications of MP exposure on various stem cell types, underlining the potential risks to human health during development (Martin-Folgar et al., 2024).

Fig. 2. MPs and their health repercussions on the respiratory system, liver, immune system, STEM cells, brain and reproductive system.

Having discussed the health repercussions of microplastics on various organ systems, the following figure (Fig. 2) provides a visual summary of their impact on the respiratory system, liver, immune system, stem cells, brain, and reproductive system.

In addition, Table 1 provides a summary of key studies exploring the impacts of MPs on human cells.

5. Microplastics: economic losses and social considerations

In addition to contaminating food, soil, water, and oceans, plastic manufacturing, use, and management account for around 4 % of total world greenhouse gas emissions. This contribution is expected to grow significantly, with plastic production potentially responsible for up to 13 % of the planet's total carbon budget by 2050 (Sharma et al., 2023). Furthermore, of the 8.3 billion metric tons of plastic waste produced, approximately 4.3 billion tons are discarded in landfills resulting in additional potential pollution of land and an annual financial loss of more than \$13 billion (Geyer et al., 2017; Nielsen et al., 2020). In addition to land-based impacts, the natural capital loss from marine plastics is predicted to vary between \$3300 to \$33,000 per ton of plastic waste annually placing marine pollution as the primary source affecting economic loss (Goh et al., 2025). Taken together, these costs contribute to an overall annual economic burden of \$19 billion from plastic pollution, as reported by the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) and the United Nations Environment Assembly (UNEA) (United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) 2021). Despite the significant financial losses associated with plastic pollution, its societal impacts are still underestimated (McKinley et S. Fletcher, 2012). While environmental groups and health organizations have explained the danger of litter pollution, the concentrations of debris continue to increase, and its consequences are becoming more evident. For example, in the MARLISCO survey which included 3748 respondents from 16 European countries, most people confirmed observing marine debris during frequent visits to the seaside, and the problem appears to be worsening (Henderson and Green, 2020). This growing pollution not only affects ecosystems but also has tangible effects on human activities. For instance, plastic pollution significantly impacts tourism; it is regarded as offensive and nasty, posing health risks that dissuade tourists and lead to substantial financial losses (Leggett et al., 2014; Jang et al., 2014). Moreover, recent reports suggest that the socio-cultural effects of the marine plastic pollution can be classified in three different categories: i) lifestyle impacts, ii) mental health impacts, and iii) heritage and cultural effects (Zabini et al., 2020). Lifestyle impacts, for example, have been connected to feelings of economic instability and decreased social bonds because of disruptions in marine-related activities including tourism and fishing. Furthermore, plastic pollution may impede marine-based livelihoods, hurting people's capacity to learn and share key traditional fishing skills and local ecological insights, which are central to fishers' identity and lifestyle. Additionally, the direct interaction of people with nature can provide rich multisensory experiences, improving mood and tourism pleasure. However, visual pollution can detract from these encounters. Plastic debris along coastlines, for example, can degrade the appearance of marine environments, reducing their visual attractiveness and aesthetic value (Arabi et A. Nahman, 2020; Bolívar-Anillo et al., 2023). For instance, Thondhlana et al. (Thondhlana et al., 2020) reported that a diminution of the psycho-social well-being was registered due to the frustration and resentment of marine ecosystems' failure to deliver functions, benefits and services to people. This decline affects tourism satisfaction and undermines sustainability efforts focused on preserving natural beauty and promoting environmental stewardship. Finally, the destabilization of livelihoods style (social cohesion, security, and cultural) could be also a direct result of the death of charismatic organisms (birds, marine mammal, etc.) after plastic ingestion (Arabi et A. Nahman, 2020), (Beaumont et al., 2019). Thus, mitigating the effect of plastic waste on the environment and marine life, requires work at different levels: i) decreasing in the use of single use plastics, ii)

Table 1
Overview of Biological Models and Findings on MPs Exposure in Human Cells.

Biological models	Results	References
Human lung tissues	-MPs in the lung were characterized using Raman spectroscopy for the first time	(Sharma et al., 2023)
Normal human lung epithelial BEAS-2B cells	-Inflammatory and cytotoxic responses -Induce reactive oxygen species formation -Reduce transepithelial electrical resistance by diminishing zonula occludens proteins -Increase the risk for chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	(Jin et al., 2024)
Alveolar epithelial cell	-Lung dysfunction -Accumulation of inflammatory cells -Increase senescent cells -Lung inflammation	(Lu et al., 2021)
Human alveolar type II epithelial cell line (A549)	-Increase of ROS -Activation of the signaling pathway Wnt/ β -catenin	(Zhang et al., 2024)
Human lung fibroblast cell line HepG2	-Cell membrane damage -Liver inflammation -Lysosomal damage -Oxidative stress -Mitochondrial impairment -Increase lipid accumulation -Liver fibrosis	(Liang et al., 2022; Chi et al., 2022; Yin et al., 2023; Cheng et al., 2022)
Human placental cells (JEG-3)	-Increase ROS -DNA injury -Cell cycle inhibition -Inflammation -Apoptosis	(Huang et al., 2023)
Human granulosa-like tumor cells (KGN cells)	-Inhibit proliferation -Induced apoptosis -Increase ROS	(Hu et al., 2021)
Human testis	-MPs contaminate the human male reproductive tract	(Montano et al., 2023; Jin et al., 2021)
Spermatocyte cell line GC-2spd cells	-Acrosome defects -Reduction in serum testosterone levels -Increase ROS production -Apoptosis	(Sun et al., 2023; Hu et al., 2024)
Leydig cells (TM3 cells)		
Human-Derived Cells	-Immune cell activation -Heightened generation of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α and IL-6	(Adler et al., 2024)
Human glioblastoma multiforme cell line (T98G)	-Increase ROS	(Murali et al., 2015)
Neuronal cells	-Neuroinflammation -Increase in lactate dehydrogenase Disrupts mitochondrial activity	(Tönnes et E. Trushina, 2017)
Mouse brain cells	-Mitochondrial dysfunction -Inflammatory turbulence in astrocytes and microglia -Dysfunction of proteostasis -Increase the risk of Parkinson's disease	(Paing et al., 2024)
Human cerebral microvascular endothelial cell (hCMEC/D3)	-ROS generation -Stimulation of Nuclear factor kappa-B (NF- κ B) -Production of Tumor necrosis factors α (TNF- α) -Necroptosis	(Prüst et al., 2020)
C57BL/6J male mice	-Hematopoietic toxicity -Disorder of bone marrow cell arrangement -Decrease in colony-forming, renewal capability and	(Zhang et al., 2023)

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Biological models	Results	References
Hematopoietic stem cells (HSCs)	differentiation ability	(Im et al., 2022)
	-Increase the proportion of lymphocyte	
	-Inflammation	
Bone marrow mesenchymal stem cells (BMMSCs)	-MPs impaired the self-regeneration of hematopoietic stem cells	(Stojkovic et al., 2023)
	-MPs alters the fate of mesenchymal stem cells	
	-Induce senescence	
Adipocyte mesenchymal stem cells (AMSCs)	-MPs lead to the loss of several stem cell properties	
	-Increase ROS	
	-DNA damage	

increasing of the waste disposal by farmers, iii) raising awareness in social media, newspapers and television and iv) developing of research collaborations with scientists engaged in social domains (Fayshal, 2024). Additionally, effective approaches to microplastic removal include the application of physical, chemical and biological methods. For instance, physical techniques, including filtration and the use of biochar, help remove microplastics from environments, with biochar being especially efficient in wastewater, achieving up to 100 % removal (Dayal et al., 2024). Chemical methods, such as coagulation precipitation, electrocoagulation, and advanced oxidation processes offer varying efficiencies and require careful consideration of several parameters. Coagulation depends on microplastic surface properties and coagulant dosage, while electrocoagulation provides high removal rates but may face challenges such as anode passivation and high costs. Advanced oxidation processes such as photocatalysis, are influenced by light source, microplastic size and photocatalyst characteristics (Uheida et al., 2021), (Cui et al., 2024). Additionally, biological methods, including the use of microorganisms like algae, fungi, bacteria, marine species, and biopolymers such as lignin, cellulose, and modified starch, can also degrade or adsorb microplastics (Sacco et al., 2023).

6. Microplastics: policy framework and regulations

Although the impacts of plastic pollution on human health and environment are gigantic, still some health impacts of MPs are uncertain. Thus, the role of environmental groups, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), industries and researchers are crucial in creating awareness to limit the significant increase of plastic debris in nature. Furthermore, governments, local authorities and legal international organizations and agencies are responsible to implement updated policies to protect environmental sustainability and public health (M et al., 2023). In this regard, the referendum and policies against plastic (Krantzberg et al., 2023) are becoming very popular reflecting a growing recognition of the need for comprehensive strategies to address plastic pollution and promote sustainable practices.

It should also be noted that the best ways to decrease plastic pollution are reducing plastic production in general and applying a circular plastic economy (Syberg et al., 2021) such as: increasing plastic production based on bioplastic feedstocks, banning on the production of specific items, reducing the use of lightweight plastic shopping bags and disposable plastic products (food containers and cups for beverages), and applying taxes on single-use plastics. These approaches not only address plastic pollution but also support broader sustainability goals by promoting resource efficiency, reducing waste, and promoting the shift towards more sustainable materials and practices. Additionally, various legislations and policies have been progressively implemented to manage plastic waste and disposal, including reuse and recycling, reducing transboundary waste movement, environmentally effective management and measures for waste minimization (M et al., 2023). The international frameworks to mitigate plastic pollution since 1972 are

summarized in Table 2.

Moreover, the Nordic Council of Ministers in collaboration with Systemiq group present in their report "Towards Ending Plastic Pollution by 2040" the 15 Global Policy Interventions for Systems Change across the plastic lifecycle (Ministers). The application of the Global Rules Scenario could yearly reduce the mismanaged plastics by 90 % and the production of virgin plastic by 30 % by 2040 compared to 2019 level. This corresponds to an equivalent of 95 % reduction in annual mismanaged plastic and 60 % decrease in annual virgin plastic compared to the existing Business-as-Usual Scenario.

The 15 policies are regrouped under five pillars: i) minimize the generation and utilization of virgin plastics, ii) remove unnecessary and hazardous plastics and chemicals, iii) expand safe circularity, iv) control disposal of waste that cannot be avoided or securely recycled and v) restrict the use of microplastics and decrease their emissions into the environment. The 15 policy interventions in the Global Rules Scenario are summarized in Table 3 below.

7. Conclusion

The pervasive presence of plastics in our environment, particularly in packaging, has far-reaching and detrimental effects that threaten sustainability efforts. MPs affect human health through various alarming pathways, posing serious threats to the respiratory system, inducing

Table 2

International framework between 1972 and 2023 to mitigate plastic pollution.

Year	International framework	Decisions
1972	London Convention	Prohibits the dumping of waste into the ocean.
1973	MARPOL Convention	Inhibits vessels from dumping garbage into the ocean
1992	Biological Diversity convention	The first international framework aimed at addressing and combating plastic pollution
2011	Honolulu Strategy	Aims to reduce the impacts of global marine debris through a collaborative effort.
2015	UN Sustainable Development Goals, Goal 14: Life Below Water, Target 14.1: Reduce Marine Pollution	Urges the UN Member States to pursue a framework of 17 global goals by 2030. Goal 14 (Life Below Water) focuses on remediation, protection, and durable employment of seas, oceans, and marine resources, with Target 14.1 serving to avoid and decrease marine pollution in all its forms.
2017	UN Clean Seas Campaign	Encourages both private and public organizations to take voluntary steps to decrease their plastic pollution.
2018	UN Environment Assembly (UNEA) Resolution 3/7	Calls on relevant regional and international organizations such as the Stockholm Convention and Basel Convention to strengthen their efforts and collaborate to prevent and decrease marine litter and microplastics.
2018	Charleroi Declaration	The G7 commits to significantly decrease the volume of plastic that reaches the ocean.
2019	G20 Osaka Leaders Declaration	Promotes the establishment of a legally binding international framework to address marine plastic pollution.
2022	UN Environment Assembly (UNEA) Resolution 5/14	The establishment of a worldwide legally binding pact aims to catalyze global action to reform the manufacturing and management of plastic, addressing their entire life cycle by the end of 2024.
2023	G7 Leaders' Statement	Declares that plastic pollution must be reduced to zero by 2040.

Table 3

Policy interventions in the global rules scenario of the Nordic council of ministers.

Pillars	Interventions			
Pillar A: reduce virgin plastic production and consumption	1) Targets to reduce virgin plastic volume	2) Virgin plastic fees to fund solutions across the plastic lifecycle	3) Application specific levers to reduce plastic consumption	
Pillar B: eliminate avoidable and problematic plastics and chemicals	4) Bans on avoidable single-use plastics	5) Reuse targets for avoidable single-use plastics	6) Phaseout criteria for problematic plastics, polymer applications and chemicals of concerns	
Pillar C: expand safe circularity via reuse, durability and recycling	7) Design rules for safe reuse, repair, durability and cost-effective recycling	8) Targets for collection and recycling rates	9) Modulated EPR schemes applied across sectors	10) Controls for a just transition for the informal sector
Pillar D: control disposal of waste that cannot be prevented or safely recycled	11) Restrictions on plastic waste trade	12) Standards on the controlled disposal of waste that cannot be prevented or safely recycled	13) Mitigation and removal programmes for legacy plastics in the environment	
Pillar E: prevent the use of microplastics and diminish the emissions of microplastics into the environment	14) Upstream policies to reduce microplastics use and emissions		15) Downstream policies to capture microplastics, followed by control disposal	

hepatotoxicity, and harming the reproductive system. They also negatively impact the immune system, neurological health, and stem cells. Furthermore, plastic pollutions cause significant menaces on the socio-economic and socio-cultural development of countries resulting in an annual financial loss of more than \$13 billion and affecting lifestyle, mental health and human wellbeing.

Moreover, while the review extensively covered the health impacts and socioeconomic dimensions, a more integrated exploration of the effectiveness of existing mitigation strategies and their alignment with sustainability goals is necessary. Additionally, future research should prioritize cross-disciplinary studies that trace the long-term impacts of MPs on human health, as well as the potential indirect effects on global food security and biodiversity. These findings emphasize the critical need for comprehensive research, measures and policies to reduce plastic pollution. Stricter regulations on plastic production and usage, along with the development of sustainable alternatives, are essential steps forward. The application of circular plastic economy along with the control disposal of waste, reduction of virgin plastic production and consumption, and prevention the use and release of MPs constitute an effective solution to mitigating plastic pollution and fostering sustainable future.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Hana Najahi: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Mohamed Banni:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Conceptualization.

Mantoura Nakad: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation. **Rami Abboud:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision. **Jean Claude Assaf:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Luigi Operato:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Malika Belhassen:** Writing – review & editing. **Leonardo Gomes:** Writing – review & editing. **Wael Hamd:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

The authors do not have permission to share data.

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Further reading

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